

CAMO-PHY: Covert Access via Modified Waveform Obfuscation at the Physical Layer

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Abstract—This paper introduces CAMO-PHY: a framework for covert signal design with a detector suite. The suite is accompanied with a channel emulator that is fully reconfigurable. This paper display one channel environment setting with five detector designs. Three are linear that focus on energy, periodicity, and statistical independence. Two more are based on learning methods. Two covert signal designs are proposed and tested against the five detector designs. All proposed covert designs go undetected under ten decibels signal to noise ratio.

Index Terms—Covert communications, physical layer security, low probability of detection, spectrum monitoring, dirty constellation, Doppler effect, anomaly detection, deep learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

SPECTRUM detector designs must be capable of capturing malicious signals in the presence of ambient radio frequency (RF) signals. Linear methods have been explored with energy based methods [1], eigenvalue based methods [2], and cyclostationary based methods [3]. Additionally, learning based methods are also considered [4]. All the aforementioned exploit statistical footprints left by covert signals. In particular, these can be based on energy or periodicity. A sophisticated design, however, will exploit the weaknesses fo these detectors going unnoticed as low probability of anomaly (LPA) waveform.

The prior work for covert signal design includes modifying existing signals [7]. Yet, these signals are typically only validated by a short list of detectors and mostly only energy detectors. Further work has been done on the theoretical limits of covert bit transmission [10], [11].

This report addresses that gap by presenting CAMOPHY (Covert Access via Modified waveform Obfuscation at the PHYSical layer), a framework for the joint design and evaluation of LPA waveforms. The contributions are as follows.

First, a configurable 802.11a/g WiFi and BLE 5.0 RF environment emulator produces baseband IQ that traces with realistic traffic patterns, multipath fading, and RF impairments. Second, a five detector anomaly sensing suite is implemented. It comprises three classical detectors and two neural network detectors. Third, two LPA waveform families are developed. Fourth, a validation methodology characterizes detection probability versus SNR for both actual signals injections and LPA waveforms.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

The section begins with describing the bluetooth low energy (BLE) signal and Wifi used in the ambient channel emulation. The signal construction is based off of current standards.

A. BLE signal model

The BLE emulator produces Gaussian Frequency Shift Keying (GFSK) waveforms [13] with a symbol rate of $R_{\text{sym}} = 1$ Msps and a $f_{s,\text{BLE}} = 4$ MHz sample rate ,producing four samples per symbol.

Forty BLE channels, 2MHz apart, span 2.400 to 2.480 GHz. Five devices are modeled in the emulator with each device transmitting one packet. The connection interval $T_{\text{ci}} = 30$ ms hops across 5 channels per event cycling through all 40 channels. After modulation, each device collects RF impairments. Clock drift resamples the waveform by ± 20 ppm approximately, then phase noise is added with a spectral density of approximately -80 dBc/Hz. Afterwhich, IQ imbalance is introduced with a gain error of 0.5 dB and a phase error of 3° .

The received signal from device k passes through a log distance path loss model and a Rayleigh fading channel. Here the contribution from device k is given as:

$$x_{\text{BLE},k}[n] = P_{\text{tx},k} \cdot 10^{-\text{PL}(d_k)/20} \cdot g_k \tilde{s}_k[n], \quad (1)$$

where \tilde{s}_k is the impaired and frequency shifted transmit signal and g_k is the Rayleigh fading coefficient. The composite BLE signal sums all five device contributions as $x_{\text{BLE}}[n] = \sum_{k=1}^5 x_{\text{BLE},k}[n]$.

B. WiFi signal model

The WiFi emulator generates 802.11a/g orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) waveforms [14]. Each symbol uses $N_{\text{FFT}} = 64$ subcarriers with a cyclic prefix of $N_{\text{CP}} = 16$ samples at a baseband rate of $f_s = 20$ MHz. Of the 64 subcarriers, $N_{\text{data}} = 48$ carry data, 4 carry pilots, and 12 are null guard tones. Modulation and coding scheme indices 0 through 7 map to BPSK, QPSK, 16 QAM, and 64 QAM at coding rates from 1/2 to 3/4. Each packet begins with a short training field, long training field, and data OFDM symbols.

Each AP transmits a 20 MHz OFDM signal centered on its assigned channel frequency. The link from AP i to the monitor passes through an independent multipath fading channel based on the Model B residential profile [12] with $L = 9$ taps. Each tap is drawn from an exponential power delay profile,

$$h_i[\ell] \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, P[\ell]), \quad P[\ell] = \frac{e^{-\ell/\tau_{\text{rms}}}}{\sum_{m=0}^{L-1} e^{-m/\tau_{\text{rms}}}}, \quad (2)$$

where τ_{rms} is the root mean square delay spread of the channel. The received WiFi contribution from AP i is

$$x_{\text{WiFi},i}[n] = 10^{\alpha_i/20} \sum_{\ell=0}^{L-1} h_i[\ell] s_i[n - \ell], \quad (3)$$

where α_i is the receive power offset and $s_i[n]$ is the transmit signal at the AP's channel center frequency.

C. Composite received signal

The monitor observes the sum of all WiFi and BLE contributions plus any malicious signal and noise. The composite received signal is

$$y[n] = \sum_{i=1}^3 x_{\text{WiFi},i}[n] + \sum_{k=1}^5 x_{\text{BLE},k}[n] + x_{\text{mal}}[n] + w[n], \quad (4)$$

where $x_{\text{WiFi},i}[n]$ is the i th AP's multipath convolved signal from (3), $x_{\text{BLE},k}[n]$ is the k th BLE device's received signal from (1), $x_{\text{mal}}[n]$ is any injected malicious signal, and $w[n] \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_w^2)$ is additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) at a target SNR of 25 dB.

All detectors operate on this composite signal. They must distinguish malicious injections x_{mal} from the combined WiFi and BLE background.

III. DETECTOR DESIGN

This section describes each of the five detectors designed in this project. All operate on complex baseband IQ samples in 1.0 ms windows with 50% overlap. 2/3 of each observation is used for baseline learning and the remaining third for testing. A spectral mask flags frequency bins whose power spectral density (PSD) exceeds three times the median and dilates by ± 5 bins for spectral leakage.

A. Energy detector

The energy detector extends the radiometric framework of Tandra and Sahai [1] to a multi subband setting. The detector partitions the received spectrum into $K = 8$ frequency subbands and compares the per subband energy against the learned baseline via a score test.

The energy of the k -th subband is $E_k = (1/N) \sum_n |X_k[n]|^2$ where $X_k[n]$ is the received ambient channel on sample n . With baseline mean μ_k and standard deviation σ_k , the test statistic and threshold are

$$T = \max_k \frac{E_k - \mu_k}{\sigma_k}, \quad \gamma = \Phi^{-1} \left(1 - \frac{P_{\text{fa}}}{K} \right), \quad (5)$$

where Φ^{-1} is the standard normal quantile function and $P_{\text{fa}} = 0.01$. The detector declares an anomaly when $T > \gamma$.

B. Max/min eigenvalue detector

The eigenvalue detector follows Zeng and Liang [2]. It stacks $L = 16$ consecutive IQ samples into observation vectors $\hat{\mathbf{x}}[n]$ and forms the sample covariance matrix $\hat{\mathbf{R}} = (1/N_s) \sum_n \hat{\mathbf{x}}[n] \hat{\mathbf{x}}^H[n]$. The eigenvalues $\lambda_1 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_L$ yield the max/min eigenvalue ratio (MME),

$$T_{\text{MME}} = \frac{\lambda_{\text{max}}}{\lambda_{\text{min}}}. \quad (6)$$

Under noise only, the threshold follows Tracy Widom Type 1 quantiles ($c_{0.01} = 2.0234$ for $P_{\text{fa}} = 0.01$),

$$\gamma = \left(\frac{\sqrt{n} + \sqrt{p}}{\sqrt{n} - \sqrt{p}} \right)^2 \left(1 + \frac{c_\alpha \sigma_{n,p}}{\mu_{n,p}} \right), \quad (7)$$

where $n = N_s$ is the number of sample vectors, $p = L$ is the smoothing length, $\mu_{n,p} = (\sqrt{n} + \sqrt{p})^2$, and $\sigma_{n,p} = (\sqrt{n} + \sqrt{p})(n^{-1/2} + p^{-1/2})^{1/3}$. An anomaly is declared when T_{MME} exceeds this threshold.

C. Cyclostationary detector

The cyclostationary detector builds on the statistical framework of Dandawate and Giannakis [3], who established tests for the presence of cyclostationarity based on cyclic covariance and cyclic spectral estimates. The detector applies two tests where if either detects a malicious signal then the detector raises the alarm.

The first test estimates the spectral correlation function using the FFT Accumulation Method (FAM) [5]. The detector segments the signal into blocks of $N_{\text{sub}} = 256$ samples. For each candidate cyclic frequency α , it estimates the spectral correlation as

$$\hat{S}_x^\alpha[f] = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} X_k[f + \frac{\alpha}{2}] X_k^*[f - \frac{\alpha}{2}], \quad (8)$$

where $X_k[f]$ is the discrete Fourier transform (DFT) of the k th Hanning windowed block and K is the number of blocks. The detector compares the normalized peak of the spectral correlation to a threshold derived from the asymptotic distribution under the null hypothesis (ambient channel with no malicious signal) of no cyclostationarity.

The second test exploits the cyclic prefix autocorrelation inherent in OFDM signals [6]. For each candidate FFT size $N \in \{64, 128, 256, 512\}$, the detector computes the lag- N autocorrelation magnitude as

$$r_N = \frac{1}{M-N} \sum_{n=0}^{M-N-1} x[n+N] x^*[n], \quad (9)$$

$$T_{\text{CP}} = \frac{|r_N| \sqrt{M-N}}{P_{\text{total}}}, \quad (10)$$

where M is the total number of samples in the analysis window and P_{total} is the total signal power. The combined decision takes the logical OR of the FAM and CP tests.

D. CNN spectrogram detector

In this project we have designed a NN-based detector, where a supervised convolutional neural network (CNN) classifies spectrograms derived from raw IQ signals as normal or anomalous. Given a complex time-domain signal $x[n]$, a time-frequency representation is obtained using the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT):

$$X_m[k] = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x[n] w[n-mH] e^{-j2\pi kn/N} \quad (11)$$

where n is the time index, $w[\cdot]$ is the window function, m is the frame index, H is the hop size, N is the FFT size,

and k is the frequency bin index. The corresponding power spectrogram is computed as:

$$S_m[k] = \frac{1}{N} |X_m[k]|^2 \quad (12)$$

and converted to logarithmic scale. The spectrogram is normalized using min-max scaling and resized to a fixed dimension 128×64 , where $X_m[k]$ denotes the STFT and $S_m[k]$ the power spectrogram.

The normalized spectrogram $I \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 128 \times 64}$ is passed through a CNN consisting of multiple convolutional blocks. ReLU is used as an activation function and MaxPool operation is applied on it.

An adaptive average pooling layer produces a compact feature vector F , which is passed through fully connected layers to produce logits:

$$h = \text{ReLU}(W_1 F + b_1), \quad z = W_2 h + b_2 \quad (13)$$

where W_1, W_2 are the fully connected weights, b_1, b_2 are the bias terms, h is the hidden layer output, and $z = [z_0, z_1]$ represents the logits.

The probability of the anomalous class is computed using:

$$p_1 = \frac{e^{z_1}}{e^{z_0} + e^{z_1}} = \sigma(z_1 - z_0) \quad (14)$$

where p_1 denotes the probability of the anomalous class and $\sigma(\cdot)$ is the sigmoid function.

A sample is classified as anomalous if:

$$\hat{y} = P[p_1 > \tau], \quad \tau = 0.5 \quad (15)$$

where \hat{y} is the predicted label and τ is the decision threshold.

E. Autoencoder detector

In this project the designed unsupervised autoencoder learns to reconstruct normal spectrograms. Autoencoder detector can detect real world Wifi signals and blocks Anomalies as it compresses (encodes) and recreates the packet structure (decodes) so it has better sense of properties of wifi signals. Here in our dataset, the input is a flattened spectrogram of dimension $128 \times 64 = 8192$ from the dataset of I+jQ converted to spectrogram images before training. The encoder maps through a 1024 unit hidden layer with ReLU to a 128 dimensional latent space. The decoder mirrors the encoder with a final sigmoid activation.

Training minimizes the mean squared error (MSE) using Adam optimiser. The anomaly threshold τ is set at the 99th percentile of reconstruction errors on a validation set,

$$\tau = \text{Percentile}_{99} \left(\left\{ \|\mathbf{x}_i - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i\|^2 / D \right\}_{i=1}^{N_{\text{val}}} \right), \quad (16)$$

where $D = 8192$. A test window is flagged anomalous when its reconstruction error exceeds τ . In the Anomaly threshold formula x is the input variable and \hat{x} is the mean value.

IV. LOW PROBABILITY OF ANOMALY SIGNAL DESIGN

The section starts with the dirty constellation method for LPA waveform. The theoretical details are described and the formulation is mapped out. After, the Doppler spoofing method is shown as an alternative LPA waveform. Formulation is mapped out.

Dirty Constellation Attack — 16-QAM

$\epsilon=0.20$, EVM=12.6%

Fig. 1: Dirty constellation example of 12.6% EVM with 16 QAM. Red crosses are intended transmission by the AP and blue possible modified positions.

A. Dirty constellation

Each data symbol s_k is displaced by a perturbation scaled by ϵ which is a fraction of the minimum constellation distance d_{\min} . The perturbation encodes B covert bits at each host symbol. The integer $m \in \{0, \dots, 2^B - 1\}$ selects one of 2^B phase offsets around the original constellation point. The dirty symbol is

$$s_{\text{dirty}} = s_k + \epsilon d_{\min} e^{j 2\pi m / 2^B}. \quad (17)$$

The receiver decodes the covert integer from the phase of the residual $r = y - \hat{s}_{\text{clean}}$,

$$\hat{m} = \left\lfloor \frac{\angle(r) \bmod 2\pi}{2\pi / 2^B} \right\rfloor \bmod 2^B, \quad (18)$$

The error vector magnitude (EVM) constrains the perturbation amplitude,

$$\text{EVM}_{\text{rms}} = \frac{\sqrt{\mathbb{E}[|s_{\text{dirty}} - s_{\text{clean}}|^2]}}{\sqrt{\mathbb{E}[|s_{\text{clean}}|^2]}} \times 100\%. \quad (19)$$

IEEE 802.11 requires EVM below 11.2% for 16 QAM and 5.6% for 64 QAM. Because the perturbation lives inside a legitimate WiFi signal, no additional spectral energy is introduced. But a hard ceiling is set with the aforementioned standards.

B. Doppler spoofing LPA

Doppler spoofing LPA is designed to immitate the fading and doppler that forms from random walks of a device or a non-stationary channel. The amplitude of the signal at time t is

Fig. 2: Detection probability P_d versus malicious signal SNR for the five detectors. (a) BPSK and (b) QPSK are narrowband signals detected earliest by the eigenvalue detector at 4 dB. (c) OFDM is wideband and detected earliest by the energy detector at 2 dB. (d) Null hypothesis confirms near zero false alarm rate.

$A(t)$. The phase has the form $\phi(t)$ for time t . The signal takes the form $s(t) = A(t) e^{j\phi(t)}$ where the phase $\phi(t)$ integrates the instantaneous Doppler frequency $f_{\text{inst}}(t)$. For a period T and time t the three frequency profiles are evaluated.

The sinusoidal profile models periodic motion,

$$f_{\text{inst}}(t) = f_{d,\text{max}} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi t}{T}\right). \quad (20)$$

The linear profile models uniform approach and recession,

$$f_{\text{inst}}(t) = f_{d,\text{max}} \left(\frac{2t}{T} - 1\right). \quad (21)$$

The smooth random profile models irregular motion,

$$f_{\text{inst}}(t) = f_{d,\text{max}} \cdot 0.5 \cdot \text{smooth}(\mathcal{N}(0, 1)), \quad (22)$$

where the smoothing kernel is a uniform filter of length $[0.2T f_s]$. For modulation, differential phase shift keying (DPSK) is used where the receiver multiplies the received signal by the conjugate of the previous and evaluates if the phase shifted closer to 0 or by π .

V. NUMERICAL RESULTS

All experiments use 3 APs on channels 6, 1, and 11 at 25 dB SNR. Baseline statistics are learned from five clean WiFi environments. The target false alarm probability is $P_{\text{fa}} = 0.01$. Results are averaged over three to five trials.

A. Baseline Covert Signal Design

TABLE I: Baseline SNR (dB) for various PSK modulations at BER levels 10^{-1} , 10^{-2} , and 10^{-3} .

Modulation	BER = 10^{-1}	BER = 10^{-2}	BER = 10^{-3}
BPSK	4	5	6
QPSK	7	9	12
16-PSK	12	16	20
64-PSK	20	27	32
256-PSK	28	35	39

In this project the LPA design and its performance metrics are compared with the covert signal design mentioned in research in reference [8]. The performance of that covert signal (BER per SNR sweep) is as follows (refer table I). We validate our LPA performance using this as our baseline reference.

B. Detector validation

Classical detectors (Eigenvalue, Cyclostationary, Energy) have been implemented based on existing work [1]–[3]. The energy detector performs better on the OFDM signal than on the narrowband BPSK and QPSK signals, as seen from in (Fig. 2). This is expected as the OFDM signal is wideband signal thus containing more energy given the same SNR. The eigenvalue detector excels with narrowband signals as

Fig. 3: CNN ROC curve showing separation of normal and anomalous spectrograms.

TABLE II: Comparison of CNN and Autoencoder Detectors

Model	Validation Samples	Accuracy	F1 Score
CNN	3200	0.9731	0.9531
Autoencoder	3200	0.7319	0.6554

well and less so but still detects OFDM signals (Fig. 2c). This reflects the fact that narrowband signals introduce a new eigenvector with a high concentration of power making it an obvious anomaly. OFDM signals will spread the power to many eigenvectors making it less obvious. The cyclostationary is the worst performing linear detector and fails to detect narrowband signals at all Fig. 2a. While exploiting the periodic nature of the cyclic prefix in OFDM, it is still not as efficient as energy or eigenvalue based methods. Moreover, since the QPSK and BPSK signals don't contain highly periodic patterns like cyclic prefixes it fails to detect them. In the real signals, all five detectors show near zero false alarm rate for the null hypothesis Fig. 2d.

The CNN compared to Auto Encoder detector performs poorly in this design as shown in Fig. 2. Attacks that don't change the spectrogram in the way our model has been trained will evade the detector. This needs to be further studied. Both the Neural network models validation results are as shown in Table II. Based on our validation results CNN is reported to have higher accuracy of 97% compared to Autoencoder which is unsupervised has 73% accuracy which gets better as we increase our dataset in future. As seen from the ROC curve in Fig. 3, the CNN detector separates the normal WiFi spectrogram from the anomalous one. From Fig. 4, the autoencoder ROC is able to differentiate the wifi and the anomalous spectrograms as well but it underperforms than the CNN slightly because it is unsupervised and reconstruction based, missing narrow band anomalies.

C. Dirty constellation performance

First we show the bounds of the dirty constellation performance using monte carlo simulations. The covert signal

Fig. 4: Autoencoder ROC curve displaying separation of normal and anomalous spectrograms.

Fig. 5: Perturbation sweep (EVM) vs BER of the covert signal for different B using dirty constellation scheme.

attempts transmission with $B \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ across a perturbation sweep Fig. 5. Furthermore, the relationship between EVM and perturbation is shown in Fig.6 where the maximum performance is clipped by regulatory requirements for EVM.

To test the dirty constellation performance against the detectors a sweep that covers $\epsilon \in [0.01, 0.30]$ with $B = 2$ covert bits per symbol at MCS 4 (16 QAM, rate 1/2) is performed, Fig.7. Detection probability for all five detectors remains near the clean composite channel reference across the full range. No detector sees a meaningful change. Though the detectors can't detect this malicious signal, one looking at regulatory requirements will flag the LPA design if EVM of 11.2% and 5.6% are surpassed for 16 QAM and 64 QAM respectively.

As expected, the dirty constellation manipulates an already transmitted AP signal so it won't modify the eigenvalues, the cyclostationary, the energy, or any of the training data that was used for the learning based method. As such, only

Fig. 6: Perturbation vs EVM with dashed horizontal lines marking the regulatory requirements.

Fig. 7: Dirty constellation detector performance with $B = 2$ at MCS 4

a detector looking at the constellation and measuring EVM can detect this LPA design. Also, compared to the baseline detector in [8], the proposed method remains more robust and effectively undetectable.

D. Doppler LPA performance

The 3 doppler LPA variants are shown for BER capabilities in Fig. 8. Differential phase shift keying (DPSK) where the receiver multiplies the received signal by the conjugate of the previous and examines if the phase shifted closer to π or 0. The three are one par with the sinusoidal slightly leading the rest and the random slightly lagging the rest. The performance for the linear, sinusoidal, and random are shown in Fig. 9, Fig. 10, and Fig. 11 respectively. Detection evasion performance is on par for all three. They are susceptible to cyclostationary performance. This because the

instantaneous autocorrelation of $s(t) = A(t)e^{j\phi(t)}$ at small lag τ is $R_s(t, \tau) \approx A^2(t)e^{j2\pi f_{\text{inst}}(t)\tau}$. When $f_{\text{inst}}(t)$ is periodic with period T , this expression is periodic in t and admits a Fourier series with nonzero coefficients at cycle frequencies $\alpha = k/T$ given $k \neq 0$. The cyclostationary detector tests for exactly these nonzero cyclic components. The energy detector and eigenvalue detectors can eventually detect the LPA with high enough SNR. The CNN and autoencoder operate on spectrograms with thousands of frequency bins. The Doppler signal occupies only a few bins at any instant, and neither model has learned to flag a faint narrowband trace.

The usable area of the doppler LPA would be after the BER of 0.05 which occurs around 5 to 8dB SNR. At this point the cyclostationary detectors starts to be able to detect the LPA waveform though marginally. To achieve any better BER then detection is risked. Conversely, if the other detectors only are present then further signal can be added up to 16dB SNR achieving the BER floor.

Fig. 8: BER sweep of three Doppler LPA variants

Fig. 9: Performance of linear Doppler LPA against detectors.

From the figure 9, 10& 11 that at higher SNRs (5dB) the Doppler LPA (Wifi + Doppler signal) is getting detected.

VI. CONCLUSION

This report presents the CAMOPHY framework for designing and validating LPA waveforms against a suite of detectors. The channel configuration was shown but arbitrary configurations are possible with the suite. Two LPA waveforms

Fig. 10: Performance of sinusoidal Doppler LPA against detectors.

Fig. 11: Performance of random Doppler LPA against detectors.

were implemented. Both showed favorable detection evasion at high SNR.

The doppler LPA showed the capability of achieving higher BER but at the risk of higher detection, mainly from the cyclostationary detector. The dirty constellation method evaded detection all together but proves difficult to achieve a BER less than 0.05. Moreover, it has a hard limit at regulatory requirements for EVM deviation.

Neural network based detectors were shown to be less viable than linear detectors but this may be dependent on training data. Future work may want to better expose the Neural network based methods with a wider range of data. Furthermore, different architectures may be considered.

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